

International Journal of Art, Culture and Communication

Journal Homepage: <https://ijacc.org/index.php/Journal/>

Experience of Wisdom and Aesthetics in Traditional Arts

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Abstract: *Traditional art acts as the conduit for understanding the truth of wisdom and its invisible and visible aesthetics as an alternative to worldly knowledge. This paper encapsulates my journey of traditional art practices. I have dived into the realm of the aesthesis and the wisdom of Divine reality in which I have incorporated religion and distinct literary works, and analyzed the beauty of this journey as a symbol of one's consciousness. These abstract hidden treasures of traditional arts have been a part of humankind since the beginning, and upon finding this knowledge we can completely purify our souls.*

Keywords: *consciousness, Divine, aesthetics, wisdom, visual art, spiritual path, practical knowledge, scientific knowledge, truth, trust, internal peace, eternal peace, morality, independent, ethics, traditional arts, experience*

Research Objective:

Highlighting the concept of wisdom and aesthetics is a different experience altogether in a philosophical context

Research Question:

What approaches can be explained by the position of aesthetics and wisdom under the subject of traditional art?

Introduction

With the eye of discernment making the invisible world visible and making me think about this infinite knowledge of vision, happiness, aesthetics, and the very existence of my soul. These great concepts embrace my thoughts and illuminate my path. The absence of this knowledge created too many illusionary ideas and consequent anxieties and unhappiness in my life. As a practitioner of visual art, the concepts of wisdom and aesthetics enunciate the complexity of understanding the meaning of the truth in its various dimensions. My endeavors created a tremendous change in the perception of my life as an artist. It's an infinite treasure of my soul and eternal timeless happiness, a testament to the transformative power of discovering my spiritual path.

“Whoever has been given wisdom has certainly been given great boon”

Despite being rooted in the philosophies of wisdom and aesthetics for the past two decades, I still come back to the day I opened this door to my mind for searching for a certain clarity in traditional arts. Those moments of contemplation and the following enlightenment revived meaning in traditional arts for me as a new, unique, and distinct way of viewing the world. It's a deep observation of the human condition, but where the literal truth of a person's life is absent. Wisdom is when one communicates through abstract thoughts but with the aid of concrete feelings. Therefore it's a different kind of truth and has various roles and values in our lives. It began with the whole enterprise of distinguishing between the artistic way of looking at the world from the literal mind and the traditional mind.

What do I learn from traditional art? Wisdom. A specific kind of wisdom. A kind of wisdom or ultimate reality or truth that perhaps I couldn't learn from any other human activity. It preserved the mystery of things whilst maintaining the mystery of the harmony of lines, rhythm, and proportion, for how things balance against each other. It's supposed to attract attention purely for its own sake and not for the subject matter that it represents. The truth of the imaginal world, its manifestation, and the spiritual realities through various forms. The form of rhythm and how it seems to touch something deeper in me. I just want to keep doing it, over and over again. So It's safe to say that I'm not doing it to gain knowledge or a higher level of intellect, but instead for the experience, the sheer joy of it, and the feelings and thoughts it provokes within me. The information is not the primary goal, of course not all truth is written nor is it scientific knowledge and practical understanding, because we all perceive the truth differently, from our own experiences. There is no one truth. It's multifaceted. Also otherwise known as Alethic relativism. It is the doctrine that there are no absolute truths, meaning that truth is always relative to some particular frame of reference. Certain truths defy other truths. If there was one established truth for every scenario, our

world wouldn't be as it is today. Humans would've never waged wars nor would there be any legal systems or democracies established nor would there be any evil hidden amongst us.

As the Holy Prophet (PBUH) said:

“I am the way, the truth, and the life.”

Here, “truth” seems to be a true representation of the world. The “truth” is something deeper. Something beyond us. Something we need to delve into ourselves for. Something that requires us to confront our fears, our doubts, and our thoughts, and make sense of the raging storms inside of us. Just as in “I Hear An Army” by James Joyce, the poetic voice is being plundered by their thoughts and feelings until they finally recognize and accept the fact that their love is gone for good. The Prophet (PBUH) talks of the pertinence of our unwavering faith in the One True God, by having “trust” in Him. And consequently, in trusting Him, you come to know something about yourself. How far can you go and with how much hope? So the idea of the “truth” which brings in a notion of trust, is a more important one for understanding traditional art. As “From the heart to the heart” means that this is an utter, sincere, outpouring of what I felt and I expect the audience to engage with it in the same spirit as me. Trust in Him to be the guardian of our emotions from the introspective journey we are about to undertake.

This wisdom has always appeared to be a mysterious power that guides the universe. It is a search for my peace, not just from the world around me but peace from my soul too (nafs). It symbolizes the serenity peace of mind and heart that the soul yearns for. It has the miraculous effect of silencing my thoughts and allowing an overwhelming sense of peace to descend upon me.

Here I'm incorporating the desire and pleasure of this internal and eternal peace philosophically. There is a connection between desiring something and feeling the pleasure of obtaining it. Once we obtain them, it is our independent moral obligation to draw a line between the two. Not to let one seep into the other. Be the guard of your moral conscience. It is no surprise that we all have desires, after all, we are humans. And no doubt these pleasures come through thought and contemplation and not keeping our mind in check. Our mind is incapable of shutting out curiosity. To want more. To never completely feel fulfilled. And that drive to get something is achieved from the heart's pleasure as well. This is the birth of Aesthetics. Aesthetics is the philosophy of wisdom and the philosophy of beauty. Aesthetics is a name for the discipline which communicates the truth from the heart to the soul. This also helps us to form a clear distinction between the exoteric and the esoteric aspects of our society: aesthetics, and its relation to the truth and goodness.

Firstly, both of these created a complexity in me about what exactly aesthetics is and how exactly it is connected to the ultimate realities. Perhaps, it is a ‘value’ ethics. As “God has inscribed beauty upon all things.” It guides me to the principles of elegance and honesty. I hold these ethical values of utmost importance and find delight in collecting beautiful things and living this aesthetic way of life. While creating such pieces, I allow myself to completely immerse myself in these beautiful moments. There are two sides to this aesthetic experience. The first is the relishing side and the other is the exploring one. Creating traditional art is a

sublime work of abstraction and it is something I can do without necessarily exploring the depths of the human heart. Even though traditional art touches on them, it is a cognitive dimension of pleasures that makes me realize that I am not just living in a sensory world, but also in an intellectual one. The goals of wisdom and aesthetics that I have talked about are very important because of my experiences and journey. If aesthetics is how wisdom is presented, and how truth comes to my consciousness, then I can account for the value of traditional art.

Secondly, the meaning is not just what the image illustrates, it also resides in the form and it is not detachable from it. In our religion, there's a promise of viewing the world from different perspectives, what we might call God's eye, the eye of intellect, or God's perspective. There is much more than theological doctrines such as God's existence. When I meditate, the truth is revealed as I experience self-purification. In such circumstances, the form of imaginal language takes over my soul. In short, great traditional arts are not just preserved for their image, but also for their implied meaning.

For me, saying my prayers every day and repeating that practice holds extreme importance as that is how I build my relationship with God and my soul. The wisdom behind practicing every day is to intellectually feel and think about the world around me. I may feel one moment, but lost in the next and that moment is the wisdom, the Haq, the Truth. Such repetition brings an aesthetic experience that gives me my version of the revealed truth. I strive to devote myself to this to enhance the essence and the meaning of being.

Finally, I am going to end with some thoughts about the intrinsic value of traditional art. Its representation provides a window into the world of imagination and rescues its subject matter from a pure conception of its significance. Moreover, It portrays the wisdom of goodness with an observing consciousness and depicts the vision of ongoing continuous realities of deepening search. It is the representation of my soul. It also distills into its consciousness. For example, imagination is to think about the absent and non-existent with your consciousness involved. Imagination is something we call in, and so it is not voluntary. But if given the command to, you will summon it up in obedience to that order. In addition to this, in my point of view, I think it is an extremely interesting exercise to understand the difference between art and traditional art practice. Works of imagination weave distant elements together. An example of this is how the brush strokes in my paintings bring human activity into relation with the imaginary world. These imaginary worlds I create strike me and lift me to a Divine realm, as perceive the vision of paradise which insights me like a pure soul and heals my fears. Indeed I have still not fully understood this but I am still on that path and I truly believe in it.

Conclusion

My oldest daughter introduced me to this book by Susan Abulhawa, 'The Blue Between Sky and Water.' It is such a wonderful piece of work that talks about the intricacies of time and the significance of traditional roots and how one can never run away from their heritage. The story revolves around the Palestinian struggle and how one specific war-torn family can find their way back to each other and formulate bonds that otherwise could never have existed. This one quote I reminisced about and was able to relate to my work was:

“O find me
I’ll be in that blue
Between sky and water
Where all time is now
And we are the forever
Flowing like a river”

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